

Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy for Kidney and Upper Ureteric Stones: A Cross-Sectional Study

Yashank Baranwal¹, Sujoy Mukherjee², Laxman Swaroop³, Rishi Agarwal⁴

¹Resident, Department of General Surgery, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

²Professor, Department of General Surgery, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

³Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery (Urologist), Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

⁴Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery (Urologist), Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sujoy Mukherjee

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Nephrolithiasis, a condition affecting kidneys and the urinary tract, impacts around 20 lakh individuals annually in India. Influenced by several factors, untreated and recurrent renal stone often lead to development of serious complications. Percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) has been proven to be effective in treating complex and large stones. This study examined risk factors for kidney and upper ureteric stones and assessed the outcomes and complications of PCNL.

Aim: To determine the effect of various risk factors predisposing to urolithiasis and evaluate the effectiveness and outcomes of PCNL.

Methods: This study included 88 patients with renal calculi. Their history, pre-operative, peri-operative, and post-operative parameters were collected and analysed cross-sectionally.

Results: The study had the following findings

1. Almost equal incidence of renal stones in both genders, mean age was 39.37 years and those with non-vegetarian diet and no access to purified drinking water
2. Most patients had shorter operating times (50% patient - 60 minutes) and no post-operative complications (83.95%), highlighting PCNL's efficiency.
3. Significant correlation between longer operating times and increased postoperative complications.
4. Larger stones (>20mm), staghorn stones, and mid calyceal stones were associated with increased post-operative complications and longer hospital stays.

Conclusions: This study assessed the prevalence of stone formation in North Indian population and its association with age, sex, and lifestyle attributes outside the stone belt region. The influence of various characteristics of stones on PCNL outcomes was also studied, providing insights for improving patient care and formulation of preventive measures to lessen incidence and recurrence of urolithiasis.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Nephrolithiasis, commonly known as renal stones or urolithiasis, involves the formation of crystalline structures in the kidneys or urinary tract, with a high global recurrence rate of 50% within five years. This condition is prevalent in Nordic countries, the Mediterranean, northern Australia, central Europe, and parts of Asia. [1] Factors influencing stone formation include age, sex, diet, environment, and socioeconomic status. The condition affects 6% of women and 12% of men over 18, with increasing rates among children due to nutritional, metabolic, and anatomical abnormalities. [2] Key risk factors include reduced

fluid intake, high calcium and sodium consumption, and increased oxalate from foods like chocolate. [3,4] Climate change and rising obesity rates are also linked to higher incidences. In India, approximately 2 million people are affected annually, with states like Maharashtra, Gujarat, and Punjab having higher incidences due to hot climates and dietary factors. Treatment methods have evolved from open surgical lithotomy to less invasive techniques such as ureteroscopy, percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL), and shockwave lithotripsy. PCNL, introduced in 1976 and refined since, has become effective for

complex cases, with advancements reducing complications and improving outcomes. This study focuses on PCNL's effectiveness and complications in the Rohilkhand region, comparing local risk factors with broader trends to aid in preventive strategies.

Materials and Methods

Aims and Objectives:

Primary: To study Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy as a modality of treatment in patients with renal and upper ureteric stones.

Secondary: To document the demography and presentation of patients with renal and upper ureteric stones and observe the effectiveness, complications, and outcomes of Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy for treating renal and upper ureteric stones

Study Design: This is an institution based cross-sectional study.

Study Population: 88 patients who underwent PCNL in our college, for a period of 1 year, were included in this study.

After obtaining clearance from Institutional Ethics Committee, all confirmed cases of renal and upper ureteric stones undergoing PCNL were selected from November 2022 to October 2023. Informed written consent were taken from all the patients. In

all patients, a detailed history was taken and physical examination was done. Laboratory investigations were carried out as per requirement.

Radiological evaluation was done in the form of plain X-ray of kidney, ureter and bladder (KUB) and ultrasound of the abdomen. All patients underwent an intravenous urography (IVU) or CT scan whatever was feasible, prior to the procedure to assess the anatomy and functioning of kidney. Patients underwent surgeries as per their allotted group according to standard hospital protocols.

Operative technique: Under general anaesthesia, retrograde ureteric catheterization was done on the ipsilateral side. The patient was turned prone, and percutaneous access was obtained under fluoroscopic guidance by the operating surgeon using a diamond tip 18-G puncture needle.

A hydrophilic guide wire was passed, over which tract dilatations were done using Alken metal dilators and an Amplatz sheath was placed into system. [5]

Stones were fragmented using pneumatic lithoclast and removed. Intraoperative stone clearance was accessed using fluoroscopy. A double J (DJ) stent/ureteric catheter/ nephrostomy tube was placed in most of the cases. [6]

Figure 1:

Various instruments used in Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy

Statistical Analysis: In this study, statistical analyses were conducted using R (version 4.3.2), with detailed methods outlined in the methodology section. Descriptive statistics summarized patient demographics, pre- and peri-operative factors, operating times, postoperative pain levels, and hospital stays, employing mean, standard deviation,

and percentages to illustrate data trends. One-way ANOVA was used to evaluate differences in operating times across groups categorized by stone size and location, with statistical significance determined through the F-test and p-values. Logistic regression assessed the relationship between operating time and postoperative complications, with p-values indicating significance. ANOVA also analyzed variations in hospital stay durations by stone characteristics,

with Tukey's multiple comparison test identifying significant differences between groups. Postoperative complication distributions were quantified with descriptive statistics, including percentages for prevalence across different groups. Bar plots and pie charts were created using GraphPad Prism 8 software to visually depict the study parameters.

Results

Demographic distribution - Out of 88 patients 43 were males (48.86%) and 45 were females (51.13%). 34.09% of patients were of age group 21 to 30 years old, with only 9 % patients above 60 years of age and 5.68% below 20 years of age.

Figure 2:

Lifestyle attributes - 60.22% patients were non-vegetarian. 15.90% patients had history of alcohol consumption. 12.5% had smoking addiction. Only 7.95% patients had access to purified water in the study population.

Figure 3:

Pre-operative findings – Patients were analysed on the basis of pain location and pain scale. 47.72% patients had pain in left flanks and 40.90% had right flank pain. Only 11.36% patients reported bilateral flank pain. 53.40% patients had pain score of 6 and 35.22% had score of 5 out of 10.3.41%

patients presented with dysuria as primary complaint. Haemoglobin levels were normal in most of the patients. Only 3.41% presented with haemoglobin less than 8 g/dL. Total Leucocyte count was above 15000 cells/mm³ and above in only 3.40% patients and less than 4000 cells/mm³

in 7.95% patients. Coagulation profile (Prothrombin time and INR) was deranged in 15.90% patients and severely deranged in 1.13% patients. Features of Renal stones – 44.31% had stone size of less than 10 mm and 52.27% had stone size of 11-20 mm and only 3.40% had stones

of more than 20 mm. 42.04% stones were mid calyceal and 40.90% had lower calyceal stones. Operating time – 50% patients had an operating time of 60 minutes, 26.13% had operating time of 75 mins and 15.90% had operating time of 120 mins. Mean operating time was 75.85 minutes.

Figure 4:

Post-operative observations – Post operative pain reduced to 1/10 in most patients on post-operative day 3. Total mean stay of patients in our study was 8.82 days. Patients with no post-operative complications had a hospital stay of 7.65 days and ones with complications had a mean stay of 14.53 days. 82.95% patients undergoing PCNL had no complications. The commonest complications in the rest of study population included, fever

(26.67%), Leakage (40%), Vomiting (6.67%) and Haemorrhage (26.67%). Relationships between operating time and post-operative complications - Logistic regression indicates a significant relationship between operating time and post-operative complications, with predicted probabilities of complications increasing with longer operating times.

Table 1:

Size of the Stone (mm)	Mean Operating Time (mins)	SD	F-value	p-value
<10 (n=39)	65.38	15.62	5.789	0.004
10-20 (n=45)	85.42	18.54		
>20 (n=30)	105.67	20.71		

Effect of stone size: No significant effect was found between stone size and operating time. (P-value = 0.29). Significant effect was found (p-value = 0.0285), with larger stones (>20 mm) associated with longer hospital stays. Higher complication rates with larger stones, with the rate increasing from 7.69% for <10 mm to 66.67% for >20 mm.

Effect of Stone Location

Operating Time: No significant effect (p-value = 0.225).

Hospital Stay: Significant effect (p-value = 0.0192), with Staghorn stones associated with longer hospital stays.

Table 2:

Size of the Stone (mm)	Mean Operating Time (mins)	SD	F-value	p-value
<10 (n=39)	65.38	15.62	5.789	0.004
10-20 (n=45)	85.42	18.54		
>20 (n=30)	105.67	20.71		

Complications: Mid-pelvic stones had the highest complication rate (29.73%). Staghorn stones also had a notable complication rate (50%)

Table 3:

Operating Time (mins)	Association with complications	PredictedLogOdds	Predicted Probabilities
65	36.89%	-0.533	0.3689
80	45.16%	0.006	0.4516
100	58.91%	0.361	0.5891
120	65.10%	0.623	0.651

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive overview of various factors related to percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL), touching on demographics, lifestyle attributes, operating time and post-operative complications. The mean age of 39.37 years and the predominance of patients in the 31-40 age group align with previous studies showing that kidney stones are most common in the productive age range of 21-40 years.

The shift towards a higher prevalence in females, as noted in recent studies, reflects changing trends in kidney stone epidemiology. A slight female predominance in your study contrasts with historical data but is consistent with more recent findings that show an increasing incidence of kidney stones among women. A high percentage of patients lacking access to purified drinking water underscores the importance of water quality in kidney stone prevention. Studies consistently show a correlation between water hardness and kidney stones. The majority of our patients were non-smokers. While smoking has been linked to increased risk in some studies, others, including ours, do not show a significant association.

The dietary habits indicate a higher risk of kidney stones associated with high animal protein intake. Vegetarian diets appear to offer a protective effect. There was no observed correlation between hemoglobin levels and total blood loss, which may indicate that other factors are more influential in bleeding outcomes.

A small number of patients had diabetes or hypertension, but a significant proportion of these individuals experienced complications. [7] This suggests that co-morbid conditions can increase the risk of post-operative issues, consistent with other research linking these conditions to higher complication rates. [8]

The mean operating time of 75.85 minutes is in line with several studies. Our finding that stone size and location did not significantly affect operating time contrasts with some literature but may reflect specific procedural techniques or patient characteristics. A complication rate of 17.05% is consistent with previous studies. Fever, leakage, vomiting, and hemorrhage were the most common complications, with fever and hemorrhage being notably prevalent. The average hospital stay of 8.83 days was significantly longer for patients with

complications, highlighting the impact of post-operative issues on recovery time. Factors like operating time, stone burden, BMI, and co-morbidities have been linked to longer hospital stays in other studies.

Conclusions

The mean patient age was 39.38 years, with a near-equal gender distribution. Most patients were non-vegetarian and had limited access to purified water. Stone sizes varied, with most stones <20 mm and located in the lower or mid calyceal regions.⁹ Operating times averaged 75.85 minutes, with complications affecting 17.05% of patients, notably leakage and fever. Longer operating times and larger stones were linked to increased complications and prolonged hospital stays. Identifying these factors aids in preventive strategies and tailored care.

References

1. Barker DJ, Donnan SP. Regional variations in incidence of urinary stones. *British Medical Journal*. 1978 Feb 2;1(6111):508.
2. Penniston KL, McLaren ID, Greenlee RT, Nakada SY. Urolithiasis in a rural Wisconsin population from 1992 to 2008: narrowing of the male-to-female ratio. *The Journal of urology*. 2011 May 1; 185(5):1731-6.
3. Khalili P, Jamali Z, Sadeghi T, Esmacili-Nadimi A, Mohamadi M, Moghadam-Ahmadi A, Ayoobi F, Nazari A. Risk factors of kidney stone disease: a cross-sectional study in the southeast of Iran. *BMC urology*. 2021 Dec; 21:1-8.
4. Gujarathi AP, Powar J, Palwe S. A case-control study on risk factors for renal stones in a tribal area of Nashik, India.
5. J. Stuart Wolf, *Percutaneous Approaches to Upper Urinary Tract Collecting System*, Campbell Walsh Urology, tenth ed., Saunders Elsevier, 2011.
6. Maghsoudi R, Etemadian M, Shadpour P, Radfar MH, Ghasemi H, Shati M. Number of tracts or stone size: which influences outcome of percutaneous nephrolithotomy for staghorn renal stones. *Urologiainternationalis*. 2012 Jul 1; 89(1):103-6.
7. Rivera M, Viers B, Cockerill P, Agarwal D, Mehta R, Krambeck A. Pre-and postoperative predictors of infection-related complications in patients undergoing percutaneous nephro-

- lithotomy. Journal of endourology. 2016 Sep 1; 30(9):982-6.
8. Kumar GM, Nirmal KP, Kumar GS. Postoperative infective complications following percutaneous nephrolithotomy. Urology Annals. 2021 Oct 1; 13(4):340-5.
 9. Hire P, Tomar SS, Kher K. Clinical Profile and Management of Multiple Urolithiasis. Int J Adv Res Ideas Innov Technol. 2017; 3(2):584-97.